

Product Rule for Multivariable Functions

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April 23, 2022

Abstract. In this paper, we consider product rule for multivariable functions.

Keywords. Derivative; Product rule; Multivariable function.

By the product rule^[1], it is

$$(f_1 f_2 \cdots f_n)' = f_1' f_2 \cdots f_n + f_1 f_2' \cdots f_n + \cdots + f_1 f_2 \cdots f_n' \quad (1)$$

where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n$ are differentiable functions.

Here, we consider the product rule for multivariable functions such as $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$.

Lemma 1. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and let $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Let $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be functions such that for every $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k, \dots, x_n)$ and $g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k, \dots, x_n)$ is differentiable for x_k . Then,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(f \cdot g) = f \frac{\partial g}{\partial x_i} + g \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i} \quad (2)$$

Proof. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(f \cdot g) = \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta x_i, \dots, x_n)g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta x_i, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta x_i} \quad (3)$$

$$- \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta x_i} \quad (4)$$

$$= \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta x_i, \dots, x_n)g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta x_i, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta x_i} \quad (5)$$

$$- \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta x_i, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta x_i} \quad (6)$$

$$+ \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta x_i, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta x_i} \quad (7)$$

$$- \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{h} \quad (8)$$

$$= \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta x_i, \dots, x_n) \quad (9)$$

$$\times \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta x_i, \dots, x_n) - f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta x_i} \quad (10)$$

$$+ \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \quad (11)$$

$$\times \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \frac{g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + \Delta x_i, \dots, x_n) - g(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta x_i} \quad (12)$$

$$= f \frac{\partial g}{\partial x_i} + g \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i}. \quad (13)$$

This completes the proof of lemma. $\square$

Next proposition can be easily proved by above lemma.

Proposition 2. Let $n, k \in \mathbb{N}$ and let $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Let $f_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), f_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), \dots, f_k(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be functions such that for every $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}, f_j$ is differentiable for x_i . Then,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} [f_1 f_2 \cdots f_k] = \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_i} f_2 f_3 \cdots f_k + f_1 \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_i} f_3 \cdots f_k + \cdots + f_1 f_2 f_3 \cdots \frac{\partial f_k}{\partial x_i} \quad (14)$$

Proof. We proceed by induction on k . When $k = 1$, the left-hand side reduces to $\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} [f_1] = \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_i}$, and the right-hand side becomes $\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_i}$. Since the (14) is true when $k = 1$, let us assume that (14) is true when $k = m$. Hence, by the assumption,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (f_1 f_2 \cdots f_m) = \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_i} f_2 f_3 \cdots f_m + f_1 \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_i} f_3 \cdots f_m + \cdots + f_1 f_2 f_3 \cdots \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_i} \quad (15)$$

is true. Then, when $k = m + 1$, we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (f_1 f_2 \cdots f_{m+1}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} ((f_1 f_2 \cdots f_m) \cdot f_{m+1}) = f_1 f_2 \cdots f_m \frac{\partial f_{m+1}}{\partial x_i} + f_{m+1} \frac{\partial (f_1 f_2 \cdots f_m)}{\partial x_i} \quad (16)$$

$$= f_1 f_2 \cdots f_m \frac{\partial f_{m+1}}{\partial x_i} + f_{m+1} \left(\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_i} f_2 f_3 \cdots f_m + f_1 \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_i} f_3 \cdots f_m + \cdots + f_1 f_2 f_3 \cdots \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (17)$$

$$= \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_i} f_2 f_3 \cdots f_m f_{m+1} + f_1 \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_i} f_3 \cdots f_m f_{m+1} + \cdots + f_1 f_2 f_3 \cdots f_m \frac{\partial f_{m+1}}{\partial x_i} \quad (18)$$

which is same result of (14) when $k = m + 1$. Therefore, (14) is true for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

This completes the proof of the theorem. $\square$

Example 3. Evaluate $\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(x^2 y + x \sqrt{xy}) \left(x^5 y^6 + 3y + x \sqrt[3]{y^2} \right) \right]$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(x^2 y + x \sqrt{xy}) \left(x^5 y^6 + 3y + x \sqrt[3]{y^2} \right) \right] \quad (19)$$

$$= (x^2 y + x \sqrt{xy}) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(x^5 y^6 + 3y + xy^{2/3} \right) + \left(x^5 y^6 + 3y + xy^{2/3} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (x^2 y + x \sqrt{xy}) \quad (20)$$

$$= (x^2 y + x \sqrt{xy}) \left(6x^5 y^5 + 3 + \frac{2x}{3\sqrt[3]{y}} \right) + \left(x^5 y^6 + 3y + x \sqrt[3]{y^2} \right) \left(x^2 + \frac{x^2}{2\sqrt{xy}} \right) \quad (21)$$

Example 4. Evaluate $\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(x^2y + x^5\sqrt{y}) e^{x/y} \cos(x^2y) \right]$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(x^2y + x^5\sqrt{y})^{x/y} \cos(x^2y) \right] \quad (22)$$

$$= e^{x/y} \cos(x^2y) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (x^2y + x^5\sqrt{y}) + (x^2y + x^5\sqrt{y}) \cos(x^2y) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} e^{x/y} \quad (23)$$

$$+ (x^2y + x^5\sqrt{y}) e^{x/y} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \cos(x^2y) \quad (24)$$

$$= \left(x^2 + \frac{x^5}{2\sqrt{y}} \right) e^{x/y} \cos(x^2y) - \frac{x e^{x/y} \cos(x^2y) (x^2y + x^5\sqrt{y})}{y^2} \quad (25)$$

$$- x^2 e^{x/y} \sin(x^2y) (x^2y + x^5\sqrt{y}) \quad (26)$$

Acknowledgment. I would like to thank my family for their support.

Reference

- [1] “Product Rule”. Wikipedia. Wikimedia Foundation, April 21, 2022.
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Product_rule.